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Psychosocial Stressors As Predictors Of Mental Health Challenges Among Undergraduate Students In Tertiary Institutions In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated Psychosocial Stressors and Their Impact on Academic Performance and Mental Health of Undergraduates in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. Correlational research design was used for the study. The aim of the study was to determine the relationship between psychosocial predictors and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. A sample of 1, 324 undergraduate students was used to compose the sample. The multistage sampling technique was used. Two research questions were answered while two corresponding null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Instruments for data collection as titled Psychosocial Stressors Questionnaire and Mental Health Challenges Scale comprising of a 21 Item self-report inventory known as DASS-Depression, Anxiety Stress Scales were used. The instruments were validated by three experts in measurement and evaluation. The coefficient of reliability for the two instruments was done using the Cronbach Alpha Reliability method of internal consistency, psychosocial Stressors questionnaire 0.835 and mental health challenges scale 0.911 were obtained. The research questions were answered using simple regression while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test associated with simple regression. Findings revealed among others that there is a low and weak positive prediction between social media use and mental health challenges but the prediction is not significant. It was also revealed that there is a low and weak positive prediction between parental stress and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State and the prediction is statistically significant. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that parents should use the right parenting styles targeted at showing love, care, support and empathy towards their children, students should use social media networks positively to build their ICT knowledge and for other useful purposes, government should provide recreational facilities for students to have leisure and relaxation for management of stress and anxiety in the school environment, students should have peers or friends that add value to them and that students should develop in themselves a resilient attitude and a positive self- esteem to overcome whatever pressures they encounter in the course of their study in the tertiary institutions.

Keywords: Psychosocial Stressors, Mental Health, Undergraduates, Tertiary Institutions,

INTRODUCTION

Before the advent of modern psychosocial treatments or intervention strategies to the causation of psychopathology, with the focus on psychological, social and cultural factors. Well known philosophers such as Plato, Aristotle, among others, wrote about the importance of fantasies, dreams and thus anticipated to some degree, the fields of psychoanalytic thought and cognitive science that were later created. They were also some of the first to plead for human and responsible care for individuals with psychological difficulties or challenges (Delhi, 2015).

From the view of positive psychology or holism, mental health may involve an individual's capacity to enjoy life and create a stable relationship between life activities and efforts to achieve psychological resilience. Snyder et, al (2011). Mental health comprises of emotional, psychological and social well-being affecting cognition, perception, and behavior. According to World Health Organization WHO, it is a state of well-being in which an individual realizes his or her abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and can contribute to his or her community (WHO, 2023). It likewise dictates how an individual manages stress, interpersonal relationships and decision –making. Mental health includes subjective well-being, perceived self-efficacy, autonomy, competence, intergenerational dependence, and self-actualization of one's intellectual and emotional potentials, among others (WHO, 2014). From the view of positive psychology or holism, mental health may involve an individual's capacity to enjoy life and create a stable relationship between life activities and efforts to achieve psychological resilience. Snyder et, al (2011) Cultural differences, subjective tests and competing professional theories all affect how one defines mental health (Mental Health, 2019).

Mental health problems are 16% of the global burden of disease and injury in people aged 10-19 years. 8.9 million young adults are affected by mental illness. 42% of those young adults went untreated as of 2018 (Mental Health, 2021). In the United States alone in 2021, at least roughly 17.5% of the population (ages 18 and older) were recorded as having a mental illness. The comparison between reports and statistics of mental health issues in newer generations (18-25 years old to 26-49 years old) and the older generation (50 years or older) depicts an increase in mental health issues as only 15% of the older generation reported a mental health issue whereas the newer generations reported 33.7% (18-25) and 28.1% (26-49). Half of all mental health problem begin by 14 years of age but most cases go unfounded and unattained to (Adolescent Mental health, 2021 & Mental Health Statistics 2021). The function of caregivers for youths with mental health needs is valuable and caregivers are at an advantage when they have enough psychoeducation and peer support (Yoo et, al, 2018) Depression is one of the leading causes of illness and disability among young people (Adolescent Mental Health, 2021). Suicide is the fourth leading cause of death in 15-19-year-olds (Adolescent Mental Health, 2021). Exposure to childhood trauma can cause mental health disorders and poor academic achievement (Larson et al, 2017). Ignoring mental health problems in adolescents can impact adulthood (Kato et., al, 2015) 50% of preschool children show a natural reduction in behavioral problems. The remaining experience long-term consequences (Kato et., 2015). It hinders physical and mental health and limits opportunities to live fulfilling lives (Kato et., al. 2015).

Some early symptoms related to mental health challenges are sleep irritation, lack of energy, lack of appetite, having suicidal tendencies or thought and desire to injure others, self –isolating, and frequent zoning out (Mental Health, 2021). There are certain factors that could cause mental health challenges for undergraduate students in tertiary institutions these factors could be psychological and also social in nature. They include social media use, parental stress, parent – child interaction, substance use among others.

Social media addiction or excessive social media use refers to an uncontrollable and excessive involvement in social media networking sites and platforms. An individual or person suffering from social media addiction gives a significant amount of time and energy to go through social networking sites and engaging with other users on the platforms, as explained by psychologists (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017).

The most common signs and symptoms of social media addictions are: Spending a significant amount of time online; individuals having problems with social media addiction may give priority to social media use over other important things that becomes their main activity, leading or paving way to an unhealthy fixation on social media (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). This symptom is linked to salience, a characteristic symptom of behavioural addictions, relying on social media as a coping mechanism. An individual may increasingly or continuously use social media to cope with difficulties or negative emotions such as boredom, social anxiety, stress or loneliness. Withdrawing from friends and family: Personal relationships may suffer as social media addict prefers to spend more time in the virtual world focusing mainly on social media, this may cause an individual to withdraw from family and friends and struggle to be mindful and attentive. Social media addiction or excessive use of the media can have negative impacts on a person's mental health or well being such as: Anxiety and depression: The most common negative result or effect of excessive use of media is anxiety and depression (Karim, 2020). The psychologist opined that social media addiction is linked to anxiety and depression. Excessive social media consumption and activity puts fear of missing out on the latest present trends. Additionally, online reputation, influenced by likes and comments on social media posts, paves way for pressure and stress that enhance higher levels of anxiety and depression. Youths who receive negative feedback or response from social media posts are likely to have or be prone to emotional distress that may develop into more chronic mental health problems or conditions (Beyari, 2023). Increased isolation: Isolation can either make people turn to social media as a preferred means of communication or develop feelings of isolation due to excessive use of social media (Yousse, 2020). She emphasized the direct link between social media use and loneliness and isolation. Higher level of social media consumption and use were linked to higher levels of loneliness among social media users. Additionally, spending more time interacting face to face with the social media can cause negative mood condition like social isolation and decreased physical activity: Excessive social media use negatively affects physical activities and contributes to unhealthy lifestyle patterns.

According to Yousse (2020) she explained that social media addiction consumes daily life or everyday life functioning, reduces or limits physical activities and impairs sleep patterns that result in poor sleep quality which is insomnia or sleep disorder a mental health challenge which when one does not have a proper sleep it can lead to depression and anxiety.

Low self –esteem: Loss of self – esteem can come from comparing oneself with seemingly perfect images of people posted online, youths may compare their life and appearance with the idealized representations of social media users. Pellegrino and Stasi (2022) explained that this situation can induce feeling of not being good enough and inferiority complex that undermines or limits one's sense of worth and confidence. Poor work or school performance: One of the most relevant signs that social media is becoming a problem is when it begins to negatively impact a person's life. Social media addiction can distract youths or students from their academic work, while working professionals may lose attention on work related responsibilities or activities and miss deadlines for significant or important projects.

Social media affects the brain by activating its reward circuitry and releasing dopamine in the process. Dopamine is a neurotransmitter that creates a feeling of pleasure. Excitatory synapses in specific regions or parts of the brain are activated when a social media user receives positive feedback online. This process activates dopamine receptors in the brain's reward centre or path ways creating or giving pleasurable feelings and rewarding the body (Lembke, 2020) she further explained that repeated exposure and short term dopamine feedback mechanisms stimulate a person to use social media more frequently to get the same impact. This leads to dependence and eventually, addiction. Other effects of excessive social media use on the psychological and mental health condition is that it can lead to increased risk of being bullied online or becoming a cyber-bully (Pellegrino, Stasi and Bhatiasev, 2022).

Maduka, Johnson & Babatunde (2023) carried out a study anchored on health belief model in Ebonyi State and it was found that the undergraduates overstayed on social media during the pandemic. It was also found that the undergraduates stayed on social media during the Covid-19 for business transactions, romance/relationships, games/betting and sports activities among other things. It was also observed that excessive stay on social media caused these undergraduates mental health issues like depression, anxiety,

headache and insomnia during the period. Also, Beyari, Hassan & Yu Sen-Chi (2023) did a study on the relationship between social media and the increase in mental health problems. The study investigated the relationship between social media and increase in mental health problems in Saudi Arabia. The study adopted the analytical hierarchical process (AHP), the researcher analyzed data to compare the impact of various social media features on mental health. The social media features included are private chats and calls, group chats and calls, browsing posts, games, media sharing, adverts, likes, comments/followers, and pages. The researcher adopted entertainment information, social interaction, privacy, esteem and communication as the criteria in the AHP process. Among these criteria, the study found that entertainment was the most significant. Findings suggested that likes, comments, and followers were the biggest contributors to poor mental health (total validity = 56.24). The least effect featured was “games” (total utility = 2.56).

People can spread malicious rumors and offensive remarks or comments through different platforms, which can be psychologically scarring or cause phobia or even panic attacks which causes trauma for the individual or youth involved most of the times, cyber bullies can cause emotional or psychological damage while remaining anonymous or unnamed. When an individual is bullied online the emotions of the person is disturbed this can lead to depression, anxiety which are mental health challenges. The person’s self- esteem is also affected in the sense that he/ she begins to think low of himself or herself. Thus this can lead to mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institution in Rivers State.

Given the increased levels of stress in parents, it is highly essential to study how parental stress is related to child mental health. Numerous studies have established a strong link between parent mental health (anxiety, depression, stress and child psychopathology). There is evidence from research conducted with both nonclinical and clinical samples that indicates that child internalizing and externalizing problems are related to parents' stress. Namely, during the COVID-19 pandemic parental anxiety, depressive symptoms, and stress have been linked to internalizing and externalizing problems in children and adolescents (Barry et al., 2005; Jones et al., 2021; Khoury et al., 2021; Whittle et al., 2020).

When a parent is stressed out it has the tendency to transmit such negative stress effects to the child, something that cannot be avoided easily due to the nature of the relationship between parent and child (Sharry, 2024). “The bond between parents and their children is many times or always extremely associated with each other’s mental health. When the parent can show they are positive and happy it can create an atmosphere of safety and security for the child. Such an atmosphere leads to greater well being for everyone involved”. “signs of strain in parents are usually manifested by signs of tension, like anxiety, quick- temper, trouble getting enough sleep and even physical reactions like migraines and feeling of unwellness” (Sharry, 2024).

Vijay, Gonsalves and Ramesh (2022) did a study on parenting styles and mental health of adolescents. Parenting styles were assessed by parenting styles and dimensions questionnaire (PSDQ) short version, and stress was measured using the perceived stress scale. Based on the mean PSDQ score, authoritarian parenting style (55.07%) was the most prevalent type, followed closely by the authoritative style (52.16%). The prevalence of moderate and mild stress was among boys and girls respectively.

“When parents are under pressure, it can have a major impact on their parenting abilities. This is because feeling stressed stops or hinders them from performing their parental role like listening and really understanding what their children are saying. Furthermore, it makes parents to become irritable and more likely to respond harshly when faced with difficult moments. (Sharry, 2024). Thus this situation can cause mental health challenges for undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It is against this background that the researcher is interested in studying the psychosocial stressor as predictors of mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The researcher has observed that many undergraduate students in our tertiary institutions are daily faced with various mental health challenges that affect the daily functioning of their lives and these problems are becoming so alarming that a lot of them are beginning to suffer from mental health problems or issues

leading to the need to take them to a mental health facility for medical care and intervention. These undergraduate students go through mental health challenges like depression, anxiety, phobias, panic attacks, eating disorders, low self - esteem, insomnia, substance or drug abuse, anger issues, conduct disorder, personality issues, mood disorders among others.

These challenges can lead to grievous consequences such as these youths going psychotic that is they begin to hear voices and see things that are not really there which are known as visual and auditory hallucinations and delusions. They begin to speak to themselves unknowingly. For some they become malnourished and look skinny and abnormal behavior is observed. Many of them look unkempt and tattered. It also gets to a point that the vital or sensitive organs of these youths become diseased such organs as the heart, lungs, liver, kidney among others and this can lead to death. These challenges are exacerbated by inadequate institutional support systems, such as limited access to mental health services, counseling, and stress management programs, particularly in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Despite the critical role of these factors, there is limited empirical research examining the interaction between psychosocial stressors, and mental health. It is within this context that this study investigate the psychosocial stressors as predictors of mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine psychosocial stressors as predictors of mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of this study are;

1. To ascertain the extent to which parental stress predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. To ascertain the extent to which social media use predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

1. To what extent does parental stress predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does social media use predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. Parental stress does not significantly predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. Social media use does not significantly predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The Correlational research design was adopted in the study. This design is considered appropriate since the researcher is interested in investigating the relationship between Psychosocial stressors and Mental Health Challenges among Undergraduate Students in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. The population of the study comprised all 78, 525 undergraduate students in the three government owned universities in Rivers State and two polytechnics in Rivers State. The sample size for the study was 1, 324 Undergraduate Students in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. Stratified random sampling technique was employed to randomly select the institution based on their respective institutions (universities and polytechnics) and the simple random sampling technique was also used to draw two departments from each of the faculties from the five tertiary institutions. These departments have specific number of students which the researcher made use of (Uniport – 353, RSU- 478, IAUE- 122, KenSarowiwa Poly – 200 and Captain Elechi Amadi Poly- 171) giving a sum total of 1, 324 for the sample. The instruments for data collection were the Psychosocial Predictors' Questionnaire (PPQ) and the mental health challenges scale (comprising of Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scales) a 21- item self reporting scale (DASS- 21). The

Psychosocial Predictors Questionnaire had 2 sections and each section had 5 parts each. Each part measured each of the 2 psychosocial predictors' variables. The first section measured parental stress, while the second measured social media use, which are a 4 point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. The mental health challenges scale is a standardized instrument which is represented as Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS) by Lovibond & Lovibond (1995) a self – report questionnaire consisting of 21 items that assess various symptoms of depression, anxiety and stress. Each of the three DASS- 21 scales contain 7 items, divided into subscales with similar content with a rating scale of: 0= did not apply to me at all, 1= applied to me to some degree, or some of the time, 2= applied to me to a considerable degree or a good part of time and 3= applied to me very much or most of the time. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity while Cronbach alpha was used to check the internal consistency of the instrument to guarantee the use of the instrument for the study. The reliability coefficients obtained for the two instruments were; psychosocial predictors' questionnaire 0.835 and mental health challenges scale 0.911. The instrument was administered to the students by the researcher, assisted by two trained research assistants. Copies of the instruments were retrieved after students had given their responses. Data collected was analyzed using Simple regression Statistic in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The r- Value (coefficient) of Simple regression Statistic was used to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses was tested using t- test associated with simple regression at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *To what extent does parental stress predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent parental stress predicted mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.073 ^a	.005	.005	.47397

Table 1 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.073 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.005. This shows that there is a low and weak positive prediction between parental stress and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Judging by the coefficient of determination which is 7.3% change in mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State can be predicted by parental stress, while 92.7% was accounted for by other variables not considered in this study.

Research Question Two: *To what extent does social media use predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent social media use predicted mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.005 ^a	.000	.001	.47517

Table 2 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.005 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.000. This shows that there is a low and weak positive prediction between social media use and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in

Rivers State. Judging by the coefficient of determination which is 0.00% change in mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State can be predicted by social media use, while 100% was accounted for by other variables not considered in this study.

Hypothesis One: Parental stress does not significantly predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Table 3: T-test associated with Simple Regressions on how Parental stress predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.032	.045		45.555	.000
	Parental stress	-.060	.022	-.073	-2.662	.008

Table 3 shows that the t-test calculated for parental stress is -2.662 and the significant P-value of 0.008, is lower than 0.05 level of significance ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, this implies that parental stress significantly predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: Social media use does not significantly predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Table 4: T-test associated with Simple Regressions on how social media use predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.904	.085		22.522	.000
	social media use	.005	.030	.005	.175	.861

Table 4 shows that the t-test calculated for social media use is 0.175 and the significant P-value of 0.861, is higher than 0.05 level of significance ($P > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, this implies that social media use does not significantly predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Parental stress and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

There is a low and weak positive prediction between parental stress and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State and the prediction is statistically significant. This finding is in alignment with the views of Bakhshani et al (2022) who conducted an experimental study on adolescent girls aged 12 – 16 years in Mahshajr, Khuzetan Provincine, Iran, in 2020. Their findings revealed that an educational intervention on a group matters regarding their parenting styles has helped their adolescent daughters to handle or manage their anxiety and depression and also led to a decrease or reduction in all anxiety and depressive scores.

The result is also in alignment with Vijay, Gonsalves and Ramesh (2022) who carried out a study or research on parenting styles and mental health of adolescents. The study revealed that according to adolescents their parents adopted authoritarian parenting styles, permissive styles among boys and authoritative parenting style among girls and this was associated with high stress levels. The result above are in alignment that parental stress has a significant prediction with mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Social media use and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

There is a low and positive prediction between social media use and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State and the prediction is not statistically significant. This finding is not in alignment with the findings of Maduka, Johnson & Babatunde (2023) who found that undergraduates stayed on social media during the COVID- 19 for business transaction, romance / relationships, games / betting and sports activities among other things. It was also observed that excessive stay on social media caused these undergraduates mental health issues like depression, anxiety, headache and insomnia during the period.

The finding is also contrary with the views of Beyari and Yu Sen-Chi (2023) who carried out a study on the relationship between social media use and the increase in mental health problems, findings revealed that likes, comments and followers were the biggest contributors to poor mental health. This result may be attributed to differences in the use of social media by undergraduate students in Rivers State and this may not be detrimental to their mental health.

CONCLUSION

This study on psychosocial stressors as predictors of mental health of undergraduates in Rivers State highlights the complex relationship between family, environmental, social, and individual factors that influence students' well-being. The research findings show that stressors such as family issues, and lack of institutional support negatively affect students' ability to perform well academically and maintain good mental health. The high rates of mental health issues, including anxiety, depression, and burnout, among students highlight the urgent need for measures to address these challenges. The study also shows that excess media use and mental health problems are interconnected, creating a cycle that requires a comprehensive approach to resolve. The study emphasises the importance of institutional frameworks in providing a supportive environment that promotes mental well-being. This requires collaboration between lecturers, policymakers, mental health professionals, and other stakeholders to create an academic setting that fosters success.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents should use the right parenting styles targeted at showing love, care, support and empathy towards their children.
2. Students should use social media networks positively to build their ICT knowledge and for other useful purposes.
3. Government should provide recreational facilities for students to have leisure and relaxation for management of stress and anxiety in the school environment.
4. Students should have peers or friends that add value to them.
5. Students should develop in themselves a resilient attitude and a positive self- esteem to overcome whatever pressures they encounter in the course of their study in the tertiary institutions.

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